

D6.2 Short explainer video about the Biowaste Clubs

Author:

Greenovate! Europe

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Author(s)	James Ling (G!E), Belen Gutierrez Carmona (G!E-REV), Carina Die-drich, Fiona Woo, Felix Schumacher, Dimitra Ioannidou (CSCP)
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Video description and link

The main objective of this deliverable was to explain what a 'Biowaste Club' is. As the Biowaste Clubs are already established in the eight HOOP Lighthouse Cities and Regions the target audience is potential replicators: actors outside of the HOOP project who may be interested in establishing a Club in their territory. A video was chosen as the medium, being more engaging and fun than alternatives such as a brochure.

The video concept and script were developed by CSCP in collaboration with G!E and G!E-REV. Video editing and production was done by G!E-REV. Due to ongoing covid-related restrictions on work travel and meetings, G!E were unable to travel to Germany for filming. As a result, interview sections had to be filmed by CSCP staff at home. Once permitted, G!E intends to meet with CSCP staff in person to re-record the interview sections to obtain a more professional quality level, before engaging in wider dissemination.

The video can be viewed here: <https://youtu.be/slaa8SGfZ1k>